

THE PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP INSTITUTE IS AN EFFECTIVE TOOL IN ENSURING PUBLIC SAFETY

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Annotation: The article analyzes the sphere of Public Private Partnership on the example of foreign countries. Some aspects of the implementation of the PPPs in the public security system are described.

Key words: public-private partnership, legislation in the field of Public Private Partnership, public security system, ensuring public security.

Аннотация: Мақолада давлат-хусусий шериклик соҳаси хорижий давлатлар мисолида таҳлил қилинган. ДХШни жамоат хавфсизлигини таъминлаш тизимига тадбиқ этишининг айрим жиҳатлари баён қилинган.

Таянч сўзлар: давлат-хусусий шериклик, давлат хусусий шериклик соҳасидаги қонунчилик, жамоат хавфсизлиги тизими, жамоат хавфсизлигини таъминлаш.

Аннотация: В статье анализируется сфера государственно-частного партнерства на примере зарубежных стран. Описаны некоторые аспекты реализации ГЧП в системе общественной безопасности.

Ключевые слова: государственно-частное партнерство, законодательство в сфере государственно-частного партнерства, система общественной безопасности, обеспечение общественной безопасности.

In the conditions of today's rapidly advancing modern market economy, public-private partnership (PPP) is an effective means of economic and social development at the national and regional level, attracting funds to investment projects aimed at maintaining control by state and local government bodies and establishing effective economic cooperation with the private sector. and is a means

of implementation. Today, we can see that public-private partnership (PPP) relations play a major role in the development of the country's economy, the effective implementation of large infrastructure projects, and the improvement of social infrastructure in the country. In this regard, one of the important tasks is to study the experience of developing countries and introduce their practices to our country. In particular, it is especially important to study the experiences of the most developed countries of the world and other developed and developing countries regarding public-private partnership relations and directly introduce successful practices in this regard to our country. The main factors that can have a direct impact on the economic growth of our country are the insufficient development of infrastructure sectors such as transport, energy, and communal services. Also, the lack of investments and the low level of involvement of modern technologies for the implementation of the necessary investment projects for the development and modernization of infrastructure facilities in these sectors are among the main problems. One of the most effective ways to solve such problems in world practice is the implementation of investment projects based on public-private partnership.

In particular, one of our national researchers, U.I. Djumaniyazov "DDS is an extremely socio-economic development for the population with the private sector based on the distribution of various economic, political, social, cultural and other risks, dangers, risks that may arise based on the long-term strategic tasks and goals of the state within the framework of the current laws, if necessary, to build politically important objects or to provide social services in this context, it is defined as literally mutually beneficial relations with the private sector."¹

Also according to the laws of developed countries it can be seen that the following legal definitions have been given to public-private partnership: For example, a public-private partnership in the United States is a type of agreement

¹ *Djumaniyazov U.I.* "Some theoretical and practical issues of the development of corporate management based on public-private partnership", scientific electronic journal "Economy and innovative technologies". 2017 № 3, My June, page 9.;

between the state and a private company in an agreed form that allows participation in public property and the performance of the functions of public authorities"². Such a contract usually refers to an agreement between the government and a private company, the subject of which will be related to the reconstruction, construction, operation and management of a public facility. The main property rights in relation to this object will not change and the state will remain the owner even after the object is transferred to a private company. The term public-private partnership describes a wide range of relationships, from contracts in which a private company assumes certain risks to complex, technically complex projects involving the construction, modernization, operation and management of facilities.

In the European Union, the term PPP is considered as "a form of cooperation between state bodies and enterprises that serves the financing, construction, modernization, management, efficient use of infrastructure of state bodies or provision of services".³

In Germany, PPP in most cases is "a long-term cooperation between public authorities and the private sector of the economy on the one hand, and resources necessary for mutual benefit on the other (for example, know-how, means of production, capital, personnel, etc.)"⁴

If we look at the experience of foreign countries, we can find different types of sectors based on public-private partnership in the provision of public security. This method later led to the passing of the Crime and Disorder Control Act in 1998 and the effective provision of public safety.

Of course, public safety must be ensured in all spheres of social life. By combining the capabilities of the state, investors and entrepreneurs, this sector can

² Geddes R.R. Wagner B.L. (2013) Why do U.S. states adopt public-private partnership enabling legislation?" Journal of Urban Economics, vol. 78. Pp. 30-41.;

³ User Guidebook on "Implementing Public-Private Partnerships for Transportation Infrastructure Projects in the United States". Federal Highway Administration (FHWA). Washington. 2007. P. 60.;

⁴Knüpfner, Werner "Public-private partnership using modern forms of management of real estate complexes". Link to the site <http://www.duma.gov.ru/sobstven/analysis/corporation/161007/5knupfer.htm>;

be brought to a qualitatively higher level. Countries with strong economies also widely use PPP to ensure public safety.

In conclusion, it is very important to properly organize the provision of the public security system in our country on the basis of public-private partnership and to define future plans for the development of this sector.

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